

Date and time: _____

Grade/Classroom: _____

Your gender? _____

Please indicate your location within the class with an X:

How do you feel the temperature of the classroom right now? Mark only one of the options with an X:

very cold	cold	a bit cold	good	a little warm	warm	very warm
<input type="checkbox"/>						
-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3

All the information you give us in this survey will be used only in the research and will not be given to anyone but the researchers

-3
-2
-1
0
1
2
3

Mark the phrase that seems most appropriate with an X:

I would like the classroom to be **much colder**

I would like the classroom to be **colder**

I would like the classroom to be **a bit colder**

I would like the classroom to be **the same**

I would like the classroom to be **a bit warmer**

I would like the classroom to be **warmer**

I would like the classroom to be **much warmer**

<input type="checkbox"/>			
<input type="checkbox"/>			
<input type="checkbox"/>			
<input type="checkbox"/>			
<input type="checkbox"/>			
<input type="checkbox"/>			
<input type="checkbox"/>			

The temperature in the classroom, right now is

Met opmerkingen [OBK1]: I think we should ch
of the questions.

Fine Not fine

+2 +1 0 -1 -2

Do you feel that the temperature of the classroom is **comfortable** at this moment?

Yes No

1 0

How do you feel the air in the classroom right now? Mark only one of the options with an X:

Fresh Stuffy/Not fresh/poor

+2 +1 0 -1 -2

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What do you think about the noise in the classroom, right now?

Not too much noise Too much noise

What do you think about the lighting in the classroom, right now?

Fine Not fine

What did you do during the last break?

sitting or resting running and playing

What are you wearing at this moment (please mark everything)?

pants	0.25	skirt	0.18	singlet	0.06	sneakers	0.02
shorts	0.06	dress	0.4	underwear	0.02	boots	0.05
t-shirt	0.09	jacket	0.135	socks	0.02	shoes	0.04
shirt	0.25	sweater	0.35	stockings	0.02	mokasen	0.03

Comments: _____

---THIS WAS THE END OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE. THANK YOU---

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